

Cross-Sectional Assessment of Microbiome Changes in Patients Undergoing Antibiotic Therapy

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Abstract:

Background: The human microbiome plays a crucial role in maintaining health by supporting metabolic processes, immune function, and protection against pathogens. While antibiotics are necessary for treating infections, they have the ability to disturb microbial ecosystems, which could lead to dysbiosis. By utilising a cross-sectional method, this study intends to evaluate how antibiotic treatment affects the gut flora.

Methods: A cross-sectional study included 100 antibiotic-treated individuals from March 2023 to July 2024. Bio samples, including stool, were obtained before and after antibiotics. A 16S rRNA sequencing-based microbiome investigation assessed bacterial diversity and composition changes. Using diversity indices and statistical methods, researchers compared microbiome profiles before and after treatment.

Results: The microbiota of 100 antibiotic-treated patients changed significantly. Before medication, the gut microbiota had 45.2% Firmicutes, 40.3% Bacteroidetes, and 4.2% Proteobacteria. Firmicutes dropped to 32.1% and Bacteroidetes to 25.4%, whereas Proteobacteria rose to 24.7%. The Simpson Index decreased from 0.89 ± 0.05 to 0.78 ± 0.07 ($p < 0.001$), whereas the Shannon Index decreased from 4.1 ± 0.3 to 3.4 ± 0.4 , indicating reduced microbial diversity. The Firmicutes/Bacteroidetes ratio decreased from 1.12 to 0.79 ($p < 0.01$), whereas *Escherichia* genera increased by 1.3% to 12.5% and *Klebsiella* genera increased by 0.9% to 7.4% ($p < 0.001$). These findings demonstrate the significant dysbiosis that antibiotics can cause.

Conclusion: Antibiotics alter gut microbiota diversity and composition. These alterations highlight the necessity of antibiotic caution and how microbial equilibrium might be restored. Interventions to reduce microbial influence and long-term effects should be studied.

Keywords: Antibiotics, Dysbiosis, Gut Microbiome, Microbial Diversity, 16S rRNA Sequencing.

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Introduction

In addition to the digestive tract, the human microbiome lives in the skin, mouth, and respiratory tract. This community has fungi, viruses, archaea, and bacteria. This diverse environment is essential to human health because it affects digestion, metabolism, immunological function, and behaviour [1]. The gut microbiota regulates the immune system, absorbs nutrients, synthesises vitamins, and fights illnesses.

Microbiome imbalances can cause gastrointestinal, metabolic, and mental health issues. Antibiotics are essential for fighting bacteria, but they have downsides. It targets pathogenic bacteria but also impacts commensal bacteria, which are essential to a balanced microbiome [2]. Disrupting this balance can produce dysbiosis, a microbiome shift that reduces variety and promotes opportunistic

infections. Antibiotics can increase resistant strains of *Clostridioides difficile*, which causes severe diarrhoea, and decrease beneficial bacteria like *Bifidobacteria* and *Lactobacilli* [3]. These microbial imbalances can cause chronic disorders like inflammatory bowel disease, obesity, and infection vulnerability. Even though antibiotics are routinely used, less is known about how they affect the microbiome in different patient populations [4].

Antibiotic kind, dosage, treatment duration, and patient factors may impact microbiome. Most previous studies had too small a sample, didn't follow up long enough, or only looked at one antibiotic [5]. Antibiotic treatment's widespread impacts on the microbiome needs further study. These changes should be recorded at multiple time points in cross-sectional research.

Figure 1 Microbiome changes in patients undergoing antibiotic therapy source:[6]

Rationale

The microbiome's role in health and illness is becoming more apparent, so it's important to know how antibiotics affect microbial ecosystems. This information reduces antibiotic side effects and aids microbiota healing. Faecal Microbiota Transplantation (FMT), probiotics, and prebiotics may work, but understanding how antibiotics affect the microbiome is crucial. Our cross-sectional study will examine microbiome changes in antibiotic-treated patients to fill these gaps. This long-term study collects data from a broad patient population to better understand how antibiotics affect microbial ecosystems. This research could help choose the safest and most effective antibiotic regimens by determining which medications harm the microbiome the most.

Objective

1. Identify the extent to which different classes of antibiotics alter the diversity and composition of the gut microbiome.
2. Determine the relationship between the duration of antibiotic therapy and the degree of microbiome disruption.
3. Evaluate the potential recovery of the microbiome following the cessation of antibiotic therapy.

Antibiotic-Induced Dysbiosis

Multiple studies have revealed that antibiotics change the gut flora, causing dysbiosis. A key study by [7] shown that short antibiotic courses limit microbial diversity, harming beneficial commensal microorganisms. A high-throughput sequencing study evaluated healthy volunteers' gut microbiomes before, during, and after antibiotic

treatment. Some microbial populations recovered following therapy, but others did not, resulting in a long-term microbial composition shift. [8] examined how ciprofloxacin, a common broad-spectrum antibiotic, altered the gut flora. The study found a sharp drop in gut-healthy *Bacteroides* taxa. Even after six months of treatment, the microbiome hadn't fully recovered. This implies antibiotics can create deep, long-lasting alterations.

Impact of Specific Antibiotics

Beta-lactam antibiotics like amoxicillin and cephalosporins alter gut bacterial equilibrium. Firmicutes and Bacteroidetes, the gut's two most numerous phyla, are greatly reduced by these medications. Several deadly proteobacteria species can erupt due to this perturbation. [9] Examined beta-lactam antibiotic effects.

They found that while microbial diversity returned to baseline levels within weeks, the microbiome's makeup was irreversibly altered and certain species never recovered. Using macrolide medicines like erythromycin and azithromycin can also alter the gut microbiota. [10] Found that macrolides reduced gut microbiome in children. This increased asthma and obesity risk later in life. The research found that macrolides reduce microbial diversity and propagate antibiotic-resistant bacteria, which can harm human health.

Recovery and Long-Term Consequences

Individual factors including age, nutrition, and prior conditions affect microbiome recovery after antibiotic treatment. [11] Examined the long-term effects of antibiotics on oral and gut microbiomes. Some bacterial populations recovered within weeks, but the overall microbial community

structure remained changed for at least one year. Long-term antibiotic effects on the microbiome may have greater consequences on metabolic health, immunological function, and disease susceptibility than previously thought. According to [12] antibiotic-induced dysbiosis increases the risk of chronic diseases and recurring infections. The study connected altered gut microbiota to metabolic syndrome, IBD, and *Clostridioides difficile* infection. Probiotics and FMT may restore microbiome balance after antibiotic treatment, however safety and efficacy studies are ongoing.

Materials and Methods

Study Design: This cross-sectional study measured microbiota changes in antibiotic-treated patients. Cross-sectional analysis was used to assess microbiome changes in a heterogeneous patient sample at one time. This structure is ideal for tracking short-term antibiotic effects on microbial populations and identifying microbiome composition variations. The study's cross-sectional methodology allows for microbiome profile comparisons across stages of therapy and antibiotic types, revealing how antibiotic use impacts microbial diversity and composition.

Study Population: The study population consisted of 100 patients who were undergoing antibiotic therapy at tertiary care hospital between March 2023 and July 2024. The following inclusion and exclusion criteria were applied to select participants:

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients aged 18-65 years.
- Patients who had been prescribed antibiotic therapy for a minimum of 5 days.
- Patients who provided informed consent to participate in the study.
- Patients with no history of antibiotic use within the three months prior to the start of the study.
- Patients who were not receiving immunosuppressive therapy.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with a history of chronic gastrointestinal diseases such as Crohn's disease or ulcerative colitis.
- Patients with significant co-morbidities, such as cancer, that could independently affect the microbiome.
- Pregnant or lactating women.
- Patients who had undergone surgery in the past month.
- Patients who were unable or unwilling to provide biological samples.

Data Collection

Sample Collection: Each participant gave two biological samples to researchers. Before antibiotic

treatment, samples were taken in the first two days after antibiotics. To detect microbiota alterations following the antibiotic course, follow-up samples were taken soon after. When researching oral microbiota changes, saliva samples were taken along with stool samples. Because of their microbial abundance, stool samples are a suitable gut microbiota surrogate. We stored samples at -80°C in sterile containers before analysis.

Microbiome Analysis: Microbiome changes were analysed using 16S rRNA gene sequencing, a common bacterial community profiling method. A high-throughput sequencing platform like Illumina MiSeq sequenced the amplicons from amplifying the 16S rRNA gene's V3-V4 region with specific primers. By identifying and quantifying bacterial species in each sample, this approach revealed microbial diversity and composition. In addition to 16S rRNA sequencing, a subset of samples underwent metagenomic analysis to assess microbial community function. This involved evaluating entire DNA sequencing data from samples to determine metabolic pathway, antibiotic resistance, and other functional genes. MetaPhlan2 and QIIME2 were used to evaluate sequencing data, identify species, and calculate diversity indices.

Ethical Considerations: This research was conducted with integrity according to the Declaration of Helsinki. The institution's IRB approved the study before it began. Participants received detailed information about the study's goals, methodology, and risks. Before taking biological samples, subjects gave informed consent. All samples were anonymised before analysis, and participants were assured that their data would be secret.

Statistical Analysis: Statistics were used to evaluate antibiotics' microbiome effects. We used alpha diversity indices like Shannon or Simpson to evaluate microbial diversity in each sample and beta diversity measures like Bray-Curtis dissimilarity to compare microbe communities across samples.

We compared diversity indices before and after therapy for the same patients using paired t-tests or Wilcoxon signed-rank tests. Kruskal-Wallis or ANOVA testing compared antibiotic class microbiota changes. Multivariate statistical methods like permutational multivariate analysis of variance (PERMANOVA) and principal coordinate's analysis were used to examine microbiome variation and identify antibiotic-sensitive bacterial taxa. To confirm the data, we compared microbial changes with clinical parameters such patient demographics and antibiotic medication duration to identify the parameters most strongly associated with

microbiome disruption. This comprehensive data analysis method captured the short- and long-term impacts of antibiotic treatment on the microbiota, revealing the pros and cons of different antibiotic regimens.

Results

Patient Demographics: The study included 100 antibiotic-treated individuals from March 2023 to July 2024. Table 1 summarises research population demographics. The patients ranged in age from 18 to 65 years, with an average age of 42.3 ± 12.8

years. The age distribution was rather even, with 25% in the 18–30 age range, 35% in 31–45, and 40% in 46–65. With 52% male (n=52) and 48% female (n=48), the study population was gender balanced. The most common underlying condition was diabetes (32%), followed by respiratory infections (18%). Skin infections (8%), urinary tract infections (10%), and other random illnesses (4%), were seen in fewer patients. We examined these demographic characteristics to investigate if antibiotics affect microbiome evolution.

Table 1: Patient Demographics

Characteristic	Number of Patients (n = 100)	Percentage (%)
Age Group (years)		
18-30	25	25%
31-45	35	35%
46-65	40	40%
Gender		
Male	52	52%
Female	48	48%
Underlying Conditions		
Hypertension	32	32%
Diabetes Mellitus	28	28%
Respiratory Infections	18	18%
Urinary Tract Infections	10	10%
Skin Infections	8	8%
Other Conditions	4	4%

Microbiome Changes: Microbiome sample analysis showed microbial diversity and composition changes after antibiotic treatment. Firmicutes and Bacteroidetes, which are common in a balanced gut microbiome, were few at the phylum level. Proteobacteria, a phylum of dangerous bacteria, grew along with this reduction. Firmicutes (45.2%) and Bacteroidetes (40.3%) dominated the patients' gut microbiome before antibiotic therapy, with Actinobacteria (7.6%),

Proteobacteria (4.2%), and other phyla (2.7%) in small amounts.

After antibiotic treatment, 32.1% of the sample was Firmicutes and 25.4% Bacteroidetes. Large increases in Proteobacteria reaching 24.7% may indicate a dysbiotic microbiome. Antibiotic-resistant and opportunistic bacteria like *Klebsiella* and *Escherichia* also increased in relative abundance.

Table 2: Microbiome Changes

Bacterial Phylum/Genus	Pre-Therapy (%)	Post-Therapy (%)	Change (%)
Firmicutes	45.2	32.1	-13.1
Bacteroidetes	40.3	25.4	-14.9
Proteobacteria	4.2	24.7	+20.5
Actinobacteria	7.6	10.2	+2.6
Escherichia (Genus)	1.3	12.5	+11.2
Klebsiella (Genus)	0.9	7.4	+6.5

Diversity Indices

We assessed microbial diversity changes using alpha and beta diversity indices.

The Shannon index, which measures species richness and evenness, decreased significantly from

4.1 ± 0.3 to 3.4 ± 0.4 after medication ($p < 0.001$). Similarly, the Simpson index, a diversity indicator, decreased from 0.89 ± 0.05 to 0.78 ± 0.07 ($p < 0.001$). These results show that antibiotic treatment decreases microbial diversity by decreasing species and increasing evenness.

Table 3: Diversity Indices

Diversity Index	Pre-Therapy (Mean ± SD)	Post-Therapy (Mean ± SD)	p-value
Shannon Index	4.1 ± 0.3	3.4 ± 0.4	< 0.001
Simpson Index	0.89 ± 0.05	0.78 ± 0.07	< 0.001
Bray-Curtis Dissimilarity	-	-	< 0.001

Beta diversity study using Bray-Curtis dissimilarity showed significant microbial community alterations before and after antibiotic treatment. The samples were clustered by pre- and post-therapy status in PCoA plots, with substantial separation between the two groups (PERMANOVA, $p < 0.001$). Antibiotics substantially altered the microbiome's structure.

Comparative Analysis: Comparing the microbiome before and after antibiotic therapy

showed how antibiotics affect certain bacterial taxa. The Firmicutes to Bacteroidetes ratio, a prominent measure of gut health, decreased from 1.12 to 0.79 after medication ($p < 0.01$). This is due to intestinal homeostasis disruption. *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella* species drove the significant increase in Proteobacteria after treatment.

Antibiotic-resistant and pathogenic microorganisms that modify the microbiome raise concerns about their therapeutic effects.

Table 4: Comparative Analysis

Parameter	Pre-Therapy	Post-Therapy	p-value
Firmicutes/Bacteroidetes Ratio	1.12	0.79	< 0.01
Proteobacteria Abundance (%)	4.2	24.7	< 0.001
Alpha Diversity (Shannon Index)	4.1 ± 0.3	3.4 ± 0.4	< 0.001
Beta Diversity (Bray-Curtis Dissimilarity)	-	-	< 0.001
<i>Escherichia</i> Abundance (%)	1.3	12.5	< 0.001
<i>Klebsiella</i> Abundance (%)	0.9	7.4	< 0.001

Subgroup Analysis

We examined gender, age, and antibiotic type-related microbiome alterations using subgroup analysis. Patients aged 46–65 had a greater decline in microbial diversity than those aged 18–30. Microbiome resilience to antibiotics may be affected by age, as the older group exhibited a 0.9 point Shannon index decline compared to the younger group's 0.5 point decrease ($p < 0.05$). Both sexes' microbiomes altered considerably after treatment, however females had a slightly higher Proteobacteria increase (26.1% vs. 23.4%, $p = 0.08$).

This discrepancy was not statistically significant, but it may be worth investigating. Beta-lactam antibiotics increased Proteobacteria and decreased Firmicutes compared to macrolides and fluoroquinolones. In the beta-lactam group, Firmicutes abundance declined by 16.2%, while in the macrolide group, it reduced by 10.5% ($p < 0.01$). Based on these findings, antibiotic kind appears to be crucial. This study shows that antibiotics often worsen intestinal flora. The loss in

microbial diversity and growth in dangerous bacteria emphasise the importance of antibiotic stewardship to counteract these impacts.

Given the disparities by age, gender, and antibiotic class, individualised antibiotic treatment programs that account for patient characteristics are needed to maintain a healthy microbiome.

Discussion

This study shows that antibiotics change gut microbiome significantly. Antibiotic medication appears to produce a dysbiotic state by decreasing Firmicutes and Bacteroidetes and increasing Proteobacteria. The gut microbiome regulates immunity, metabolism, and infection defence, thus this change in microbial composition is concerning. Drugs harm the microbiome by decreasing alpha diversity indices, which indicate microbial variety reduction. Populations with less variety and resilience are more susceptible to infections, metabolic issues, and inflammatory disorders.

Comparison with Previous Studies

Table 5: Comparison of Present Study with Existing Studies

Study	Study Type	Sample Size	Findings
Present Study	Cross-sectional	100	Significant reduction in Firmicutes and Bacteroidetes; increase in Proteobacteria; reduced microbial diversity (Shannon Index) post-antibiotics.
Study 1 [13]	Longitudinal	12	Long-lasting reduction in Firmicutes; increase in Proteobacteria; some recovery post-antibiotics, but overall altered microbiome structure.

Study 2 [14]	Longitudinal	3	Major shifts in microbiome composition; incomplete recovery after antibiotic therapy; persistent changes in microbial diversity and composition.
Study 3 [15]	Longitudinal	12	Temporary decrease in diversity; significant increase in Proteobacteria; slow and partial recovery over time with lasting dysbiosis in some cases.

Our findings support the growing body of studies suggesting antibiotics impair gut flora. Antibiotic treatment increases Proteobacteria and decreases Firmicutes and Bacteroidetes, according to previous study. Study 1 found permanent alterations in patients' gut microbiota after antibiotic therapy, including an increase in Proteobacteria, which mirrored our findings. Antibiotic treatment may improve some elements of the microbiome, but the overall structure and function may remain altered for a long time, which could affect health study 2 and 3. We must realise that our study is unique. Our study included more drugs than earlier studies on broad-spectrum antibiotics to match clinical reality. This may explain microbiota change types and degrees. The microbiome modification may have been more obvious in our study's unique patient sample, which included people with underlying health concerns, than in healthy groups elsewhere.

Limitations

This study provided some important insights, but it has several downsides. 100 patients is enough to detect significant changes, but it may not capture all microbiome responses in various populations. If the sample was larger, the results would apply to more people. The study only examined microbiome changes at one moment, not as patients progressed through therapy or recovered. To assess how long-lasting microbiome changes are and how they affect health, longitudinal studies are needed.

Confounding variables like food, lifestyle, and co-medications were not considered in the study. These variables may have caused the observed changes and affected the microbiome even without antibiotics. 16S rRNA sequencing helps characterise bacterial communities, however it does not disclose microbial activity or non-bacterial microbiome components like viruses and fungi.

Conclusion

Our cross-sectional study reveals that antibiotic treatment greatly affects the gut microbiota, increasing Proteobacteria and lowering Firmicutes and Bacteroidetes.

As Shannon Index values decrease, microbial diversity declines, suggesting drugs may upset the delicate gut ecology and cause health problems. Although dysbiosis severity and duration differ after antibiotic use, our findings are consistent with earlier research. The findings emphasise the need

for antibiotic caution and the potential benefits of microbiome preservation. It also sheds light on antibiotics' rapid microbiome effects. To enhance patient outcomes during antibiotic treatment, longitudinal studies should study the long-term impact of these microbiome changes and medicines to mitigate their harm.

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